

The Role of a Reading Specialist in the Poly-disciplinary Context

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this conceptual paper is to provide a better and clearer understanding of the role of a reading specialist in a poly-disciplinary (ranging from intra-disciplinary through cross-disciplinary, multi-disciplinary, inter-disciplinary to trans-disciplinary) context where he/she works. It begins with the definition and the role of a reading specialist as provided by the International Reading Association (now known as the International Literacy Association) its official position statement published in 2000. The paper also touches on the RSAS framework of professional role of a reading specialist in the Singapore context for its members. In addition, the learning activity system (LAS) is also used to show the professional role played by the reading specialist in terms of the three key responsibilities of service, treatment and resource provision within the systemic context.

Key words: *disciplinarity, learning activity system, reading specialist, resource, service, treatment*

INTRODUCTION

As the world moved very quickly into the new millennium to settle down, the demands on reading specialists in the domain of literacy education have also changed and become more complex than before. Gone were the days when all we were concerned were the three R's, i.e. reading, writing and arithmetic. Then came the Computer Age and computer literacy became an in-thing that every child must acquire. It constitutes the fourth R and still is today. It is not surprising to take note that robotics will soon be the fifth R in the near future.

Whatever the world is going to become in the future, we know that the underlying foundation will still be literacy and numeracy. Throughout the world, the students from different countries are constantly being ranked by such institutional instruments like the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) and the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS). Without even as basic as functional literacy, an individual living in today's world will find himself/herself completely out of touch or out of sync with the rest of the world. Perhaps illiteracy or poor literacy might soon be classified as a form of disability or disorder and can be termed as *dysliteracy*!

Our concern today and more so in Singapore is what do we expect our children to acquire in terms of knowledge and skills to prepare them for the challenging future ahead? As long as they are at risk of low or poor literacy, their academic performance is going to be adversely affected.

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We have now allied educators (teaching and learning), who play the role of teacher aides, to assist classroom teachers in a class of about 40 students during lesson. For students with learning and behavioural challenges, we have allied educators (learning and behaviour support) to provide additional assistance. For students with socio-emotional issues, there are school counsellors to work with them. In every mainstream school from primary level to pre-university level, there is now a Head of Department designated for pupil welfare and this is something unheard of back in the 1980s and earlier decades.

What about other allied professionals who also work with students in our mainstream as well as special schools? They include social workers, youth workers, probation officers, librarian, job coaches, psychologists, educational therapists and the list of these professionals and paraprofessionals can go on. Among them on the list is the reading specialist, which is not widely known or acknowledged here, but this specific professional can offer as an additional resource person to both parents and teachers as well as their children or students. A reading specialist is also known as literacy coach in the United States.

READING SPECIALISTS

In Singapore, reading specialists came into existence in 1994 when the Ministry of Education set up its School Psychological Service. That time, it employed four reading specialists in addition to its team of educational psychologists and counsellors. However, the designation of reading specialist was soon changed to reading officer because it was not easy to find a qualified or certified professional reading specialist like that in the United States. There was no official program of any kind being offered by any formal institution (e.g., teacher training institution, polytechnic or university) to train people interested in becoming reading specialists. Hence, it was very much up to individuals interested to pursue the career of a reading specialist to go overseas to complete a post-graduate program in reading education or language and literacy arts education at a tertiary institution.

What is a Reading Specialist?

Who can be a reading specialist? What does a reading specialist do? What are the necessary qualifications needed to become a reading specialist? Is there a proper professional body to represent this group of professionals?

The International Reading Association or IRA for short (now known as International Literacy Association) was the body that represented the reading teachers as well as reading specialists including those who are involved in language and literacy education. It still represents the reading professionals. Other professional bodies in Singapore include the Society for Reading (SRL) and Literacy and the Reading Specialists' Association Singapore (RSAS), which is a break-off from the SRL, which, in turn, is an associate member of the IRA.

The IRA (2000) has defined reading specialists as “professionals with advanced preparation and experience in reading who have responsibility for the literacy performance of readers in general and struggling readers in particular. This includes early childhood, elementary, middle, secondary, and adult learners. Learners can be in public, private, and commercial schools, or in reading resource centres or clinics” (cited in Reading Rockets, n.d., para.3).

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To become a reading specialist, one must have advanced degrees (e.g., post-graduate qualifications such as master's degree, specialist degree or even doctorate in reading) or post-graduate qualifications (e.g., graduate certificate or diploma, post-graduate certificate or diploma) requiring the applicant to have at least a relevant bachelor's degree (e.g., education, psychology, sociology, counselling). Depending on the legislative requirements in different states in the United States, there is also a need to obtain a practicing license or what is known as a Certificate of Professional Proficiency (CoPP) here to practice as a reading specialist.

More importantly, reading specialists are the best professionals to help prevent reading failure of at-risk students in school. Most reading specialists are registered teachers themselves and so they are well trained and qualified in pedagogy. Other teachers, who have obtained additional qualifications in areas such as Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL), Teaching English as a Second Language (TESL), and other language-related specializations, are also eligible to become a reading specialist after fulfilling the required academic credits in reading education at a college or university.

The Role of a Reading Specialist

There are many tasks that a reading specialist has to deliver. The main responsibility is to teach all children to read and that means to provide them with excellent reading instruction and material. This is best done in a school context although such service can also be offered at a reading clinic or learning centre outside school. Within the school context, a reading specialist must be mindful of the ecological system at play and may encounter those with various developmental, physical, emotional, sensory and educational needs, and hence, they require different treatment models to work with them.

As a result, reading specialists must be able to provide expert instruction, assessment and leadership for the reading programs they are going to offer and run in school. They are the resource person that both parents and teachers will turn to for advice and assistance. The IRA (2000) has provided three key roles that a reading specialist must play (see Figure 1 below): instruction, assessment and leadership.

Figure 1. The Three Key Roles of a Reading Specialist

Instruction. This refers to the role of a reading specialist to support, supplement and extend his/her service as a literacy coach into classroom teaching. However, it is important for the school administration to define the professional boundaries for both teachers and reading specialists as clearly as possible to avoid any unseen conflicts between the two professional groups. The teachers should continue to run and manage their respective classroom activities

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while the reading specialists should come in only when the teachers request them for their assistance.

Chia (2007) has provided a hierarchy of reading knowledge ranging from the lowest level that concerns letter knowledge through word knowledge and topic knowledge to background knowledge and prior experience (see Figure 2). At each level, the instructional support, supplement and extension provided by the reading specialist will be different for different readers depending on their respective levels of reading, i.e., hearing capacity level, frustration level, instructional level and independent level, that can be determined by the administration of an informal reading inventory (e.g., Classroom Reading Inventory and Abecede Reading Inventory). This brings us to the next role of a reading specialist and that is assessment.

Figure 2. Hierarchy of Reading Knowledge (Chia, 2007)

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Assessment. As a reading specialist, the professional has been trained to with specialized content knowledge and skills in terms of diagnostic assessment using both formal or standardized tools (e.g., Neale Analysis of Reading Ability, GAP Reading Comprehension Test and Gray Oral Reading Test) and informal tools (e.g., Reading Placement Inventory and Informal Reading Inventories) to determine a reader's strengths and needs, development of an individualized reading plan (IRP) and reading program (e.g., buddy reading program), implementation of the IRP and/or reading program, evaluation of the IRP and literacy program in general, and provision of relevant resources that are useful to both parents and teachers as well as allied professionals such as psychologists, allied educators, learning support coordinators and school counsellors to work those children who are struggling with reading or other literacy skills.

Chia (2007) has provided a list of formal and informal assessment tools that reading specialists can administer for each of the four levels of reading knowledge (see Figure 3).

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Figure 3. Examples of Assessment Tools for Each level in the Hierarchy of Reading Knowledge

Leadership. As already mentioned above, the reading specialist plays an important role as a leader in educational resources to other educators, parents and the community. He/She can also take the lead to link the school where he/she is stationed with the Reading Initiative directorate of the National Library Board, Singapore, to start the kidsREAD program for at-risk children from low-income of dysfunctional families in school.

The Reading Specialists' Association Singapore (RSAS), in 2012, has proposed its own framework for the professional role of a reading specialist for its members (see Figure 4):

Figure 4. RSAS Framework for the Professional Role of a Reading Specialist

In this framework, the reading specialist's leadership role is split into three key responsibilities: (1) service, (2) treatment, and (3) resource. Each of these responsibilities will be briefly discussed below.

Responsibility of Service for a Reading Specialist

Under the service responsibility, the reading specialist is to assess an individual with suspected reading challenges, develop appropriate plan of action (known as the Individualized Reading Plan or IRP for short), implement the IRP through any reading program currently being offered or any other intervention program available, and finally evaluate the progress of the individual after having undergone the reading or intervention program by re-looking at the aim, goals and/or objectives set in the IRP.

An IRP is an adaptation from the model of an Individualized Education Plan (IEP). It is a written document that describes the reading treatment program and/or specialized services required by an individual diagnosed or assessed with reading difficulties. The IRP helps to identify reading expectations modified from or alternative to the expectations that have been determined by the administration of an informal reading inventory (IRI) for the appropriate reading level, i.e, hearing capacity level, frustration level, instructional level and independent level (Emmett, 1949), and/or any access arrangement services needed to assist the individual in achieving his/her reading expectations.

Responsibility of Treatment for a Reading Specialist

Under the treatment responsibility, the reading specialist is to support, supplement and extend classroom teaching, and work collaboratively to implement a quality reading or intervention program that is research-based and meets the needs of the individual concerned (IRA, 2000).

The appropriate treatment for an individual with reading difficulties can be decided basing on the reading level determined by the administration of an informal reading inventory. As mentioned earlier, there are four levels of criteria on reading performance developed by Emmett (1949) and each of these levels is briefly described below:

Hearing capacity level: At this level, an examinee can comprehend so long as he/she does not have word recognition difficulties. To determine this level, a reading specialist reads aloud passages to the examinee until the latter's listening comprehension score falls below 70 percent of accuracy. The score on the IRI will be able to provide the score.

Frustration level: The examinee is frustrated by the difficulties he/she encounters in word recognition or comprehension. Generally, the criteria for this level are (1) below 90 percent of accuracy for word recognition, and (2) below 70 percent of accuracy for comprehension.

Instructional level: At this level of reading performance, the examinee requires direct and systematic instruction in order to make continuous progress in his/her reading performance. The criteria for this level are (1) between 90 to 95 percent for word recognition, and (2) 70 to 85 percent of accuracy for comprehension.

Independent level: At this level of reading performance, the examinee does not need help in both his/her oral reading and comprehension. The criteria for this level are (1) 95 to 100 percent of accuracy for word recognition, and (2) 90 to 100 percent of accuracy for comprehension.

Responsibility of Resource Provision for a Reading Specialist

Finally, under resource provision responsibility, the reading specialist must be proactive and resourceful in his/her networking with other allied professionals outside school so that he/she can have access to a wide or teaching resources and materials that can be used in his/her professional work.

READING SPECIALIST IN A POLY-DISCIPLINARY CONTEXT

What does the term *poly-disciplinarity* mean? Its prefix *poly-* means “many” while *disciplinarity* refers to “the state of being disciplinary” that comes from the word *discipline* which means “subject area”. The whole term *poly-disciplinarity* refers to the working state or system of many different disciplines of content knowledge and professional skills. According to Stember (1991), there are five different disciplinarity as listed below:

1. Intra-disciplinarity: working within a single discipline;
2. Cross-disciplinarity: viewing one discipline from the perspective of another;
3. Multi-disciplinarity: people from different disciplines working together, each drawing on their disciplinary knowledge and skills;

4. Inter-disciplinarity: integrating knowledge and methods from different disciplines, using a real synthesis of approaches; and
5. Trans-disciplinarity: creating a unity of intellectual framework beyond the disciplinary perspectives.

According to Jensenius (2012) and Choi and Pak (2006), there are differences among the five disciplinaritys. The three most commonly preferred ones fall within the same continuum in collaborative teamwork approach: (1) The multi-disciplinarity that draws on knowledge from different disciplines but stays within their boundaries; (2) The inter-disciplinarity that analyses, synthesizes and harmonizes links between disciplines into a coordinated and coherent whole; and (3) The trans-disciplinarity that integrates the natural, social and health sciences in the context of humanities, and transcends their traditional boundaries (Choi & Pak, 2006).

Zeigler (1990) has summarized the five different disciplinaritys into the following Figure 5:

Figure 5. The Five Disciplinaritys

In a poly-disciplinary context (be it inter-, cross-, multi- or trans-disciplinarity), a reading specialist cannot work in isolation from the other professionals or paraprofessionals, and certainly, not without the client and the client’s family. Chia (2010) has put forth three reasons why that is so and these have become the guiding principles for the treatment responsibility of a reading specialist. These three principles of treatment are briefly described below.

The first principle known as the Principle of Targeted Treatment states that “[I]f you know about the disability, disorder or problem and are also mindful of how much you know about its variant and non-variant traits, you are in a better position to prepare a good treatment with no fear of failure” (Chia, 2010, p.124). It is important for a reading specialist to work collaboratively with other professionals such as teachers, counsellors and psychologists who can provide useful information used in identifying issues pertaining to reading difficulties or other related challenges which may include low motivation and poor attitude towards reading.

The second principle known as the Principle of Symptomatic Treatment states that “If you are ignorant of the disability, disorder or problem but are aware of how much you know about its variant and non-variant traits basing on your own observation and dealing with the client, your chances of success or failure in the treatment are equal” (Chia, 2010, p.124). Whether or not a reading specialist is trained or equipped to work with an individual diagnosed with dyslexia, it is

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good if the reading specialist notices the signs and symptoms that are affecting the reading performance of that individual. In this way, by treating the symptoms (e.g., poor word recognition and erratic spelling) using known conventional strategies such as syllabication, onsets and rimes and word families, the reading specialist can still help the individual to learn to decipher words and eventually learn to read on his/her own.

The third and last principle known as the Principle of Sure Chaotic Treatment states that “If you are ignorant of the disability, disorder or problem and are also unaware of its variant and non-variant traits, *and you have not even worked with the client*, you are sure to fail in treating the condition. At all cost, this last principle should warn us who aren’t well informed or trained to help children with disabilities, disorders or problems to offer any ill advice or poorly designed treatment that can become detrimental to clients with learning & behavioural challenges” (Chia, 2010, p.124; words in italic are additional). In this instance, it is better for a collaborative team approach because there will be at least someone among the group to know the condition and able to take the lead to manage the case properly.

THE LEARNING ACTIVITY SYSTEM (LAS) FOR READING SPECIALISTS

In providing appropriate service and treatment with right resources to individuals with reading difficulties, there is a need for a suitable learning activity system (LAS) designed to meet their learning and behavioural needs in order for them to benefit from the services rendered to them and treatment they are undergoing (Chia et al., 2013). By LAS, it refers to a collective construction that is not reducible to discrete individual actions (Leontév, 1974). It can be a continuous, goal-centred/directed, historically conditioned, dialectically formatted, tool-mediated human interaction, e.g., a treatment, an IRP, a reading program, a learning centre, and so on (Chia et al., 2013; Russell, 1997). According to Engestrom (1987), LAS can be broken down into four subsystems: production, consumption, distribution, and exchange, with the following interacting components: subject/client, object/goal, tools, division of labour/work, community, rules, and the guiding agent/mediator (see Figure 6). These subsystems and their interacting components will be briefly discussed below.

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Figure 6. The Learning Activity System

Production subsystem. Briefly, this subsystem consists of the object/goal to guide the subject/client using the tools provided by a professional (e.g., the reading specialist) to produce the target outcome at the end of a treatment.

Consumption subsystem. This involves the subject/client and the community of professionals working with him/her to attain the object/goal set for the treatment.

Distribution subsystem. This refers to the division and delegation of work or tasks among the professionals working collaboratively to provide the treatment for the subject/client.

Exchange Subsystem. This refers to the rules and protocols that the respective professionals within the community have to adhere strictly according to their respective professional bodies, which may restrict them from stepping out of their professional boundaries of practice, during the process of treatment they are providing.

Subject/client as a component. This refers to an individual who is engaged in some kind of a treatment. The subject/client possesses cognitive, conative, affective and sensory potentials are brought into the LAS.

Object/goal as a component. In a treatment program, a semester goal (for six months) or term objective (for ten weeks) is set to attain certain skills. For example, by the end of the first semester, the subject/client will be able to recognize and read all the 50 sight words selected from the set of First Grade readers.

Tools as a component. These are the means used by the subject/client to achieve the object/goal of the treatment.

Community as a component. This refers to a collaborative team of professionals taking a chosen poly-disciplinary (i.e., cross-, inter-, multi-, or trans-disciplinary) approach in the provision of services and treatment.

Division of labour/work as a component. It refers to the division and delegation of tasks among the community of professionals working collaboratively to provide services and treatment needed by the subject/client. The reading specialist will have his/her job scope clearly defined so that he/she knows exactly what is to be done.

Rules as a component. These refer to the explicitly stated regulations and conventions as well as policies, the code of practice ethics and professional conduct that constrain the treatment activities being carried out by members of the collaborative team of professionals including the reading specialist.

Guiding agent/mediator as a component. This refers to any professional in the collaborative team who will serve as a guide to lead the individual (i.e., the subject/client) through the process of treatment to realize the objective/goal in order to achieve the target outcome. A reading

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specialist can be a guiding agent or mediator depending on the needs of the subject/client needs, e.g., analytic phonics instruction provided by the reading specialist for the treatment of an individual with reading difficulties.

CONCLUSION

If a reading specialist is new and inexperienced, it is better for him/her to work collaboratively with other professionals so that he/she can learn more than what he/she has already known or been trained to do. The reading specialist has to work (loosely or not) as a member of a collaborative teamwork in whichever context he/she is placed – e.g., school, learning clinic or early intervention centre – involving different professionals to come together to offer their respective expertise in terms of their disciplinary knowledge and skills. Hence, today's collaborative teamwork includes different types of disciplinarity and depends on the selected disciplinarity which reflects the management philosophy that runs the organization such as a clinic, hospital or school.

In each of the poly-disciplinary approaches (excluding the intra-disciplinary approach), the objectives designed for approach that provides service, treatment and/or resource will be different. For instance, if the reading specialist works in a team that adopts the multi-disciplinary approach, the objectives of the approach will be different from that of another that of inter-disciplinary or trans-disciplinary. Here are some examples of the objectives designed for the multi-disciplinary approach (Choi & Pak, 2006): to resolve real complex problems with inputs from different fields of expertise; to provide different perspective on problems; to create comprehensive multi-faceted questions for further research on the issues of concern; to develop conscious clinical definitions and guidelines for a holistic treatment; and to provide comprehensive services from a concerted effort of different professionals needed to address the issues identified.

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